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lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
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Food or Dietary Supplement for Stronger Respiratory System, Cardiovascular System, Memory and Sexual Health Booster

¹Datu KRESMEDEREH INV. RONIE MORATO ER-ER, ²BAE MINDARA JASSTENE NICOLE C. ER-ER, ³LORD IVEEN T. MAYBUENA, ⁴NILO P. DEMEREY JR., MPM

^{1,2}Supreme Order of Whitestone Researchers Authors Innovators Netizens for Peace & Economic Resilience, Inc. (WHITESTONE RAINPER)

^{3,4}Provincial Government of Dinagat Islands

Corresponding Email: ronie.erer@deped.gov.ph

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Abstract.

The novelty of the utility model was the development of functionalized food or dietary supplement for stronger respiratory system, cardiovascular system, and dementia prevention which were components on Weight by Volume (W/v) ratio of the trio phase comprising of; Phase 1 a component particularly herbs comprising of liquified Lagundi 20% (*Vitex negundo*), Oregano 20% (*Origanum majorama*), Kalabo 20% (*Coleus aromaticus*), Collagen 20% Kalamansi 5% (*Citrofortunelle macrocarpa*), Ginger 5% (*Zingiber officinale*), Cane 5% (*Saccharum officinarum*) for healthy respiratory system; Phase 2 a component comprising of Turmeric 20% (*Curcuma longa*) and Banaba 10% (*Lagerstroemia speciosa*), which will replace Lagundi and Kalabo to shift to Cardiovascular protection; Phase 3 a component comprising of; Gotu kola 20% (*Centella asiatica*), Cacao 20% (*Theobroma cacao*), Maca 10% (*Lepidium meyenii*), Tongkat ali 5% (*Eurycoma longifolia*), L-Argine 5%, L-Citruline 5%, for memory and sexual health. This herbal formulation utilizes thermo-controlled RONIER Phytoionic Propulsion Technology™ extraction, followed by a dry sprayer system to powder the extract. The product's packaging is used for coffee, tea, herbal juice drinks and for encapsulation and vacuum packaging to extend shelf life for storage.

Keywords: Functionalized Food, Herbal Dietary Supplement, Respiratory and Cardiovascular Health, Memory Enhancement, Sexual Health Booster